

Synthesis and antiinflammatory evaluation of some imino-sugars of methylbenzimidazole

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Various aldoses **2** were reacted with 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole **1** to give the corresponding imino-sugar methylbenzimidazoles **3a-g**. The antiinflammatory activity of the prepared compounds was studied.

The incorporation of an imidazole nucleus, a biologically accepted pharmacophore, in the benzimidazole molecule has made it a versatile heterocycle possessing a wide spectrum of biological activity^{1,2}. Recently, a large variety of 2-substituted benzimidazoles have been found to possess antiinflammatory³, antispasmodic⁴, antihistaminic⁵, antimicrobial⁶⁻⁸, antitumor⁹, anticancer¹⁰, cyclooxygenase inhibitory¹¹ and HIV-1 reverse transcriptase inhibitory¹² activities. The combination with carbohydrate units offers a possibility to equip achiral heterocycles with a hydrophilic and chiral moiety. Such functionalized heterocycles, e.g. saccharidic 1,2,4-triazinediones, are of interest due to their biological activity¹³⁻¹⁶. Depending on these findings, the present work describes the synthesis of a series of imino-sugar methylbenzimidazoles. This work also describes the antiinflammatory activity of the prepared compounds.

arabinose, L-arabinose, D-ribose, D-xylose, D-galactose, D-glucose, or D-mannose in ethanol. The products (**3a-g**) showed bands at 3445–3401 (OH), 3300–3283 (NH) and 1645–1630 cm⁻¹ (C=N) in IR region. In addition, ¹H NMR spectra of **3c** and **3e** revealed the characteristic signals: singlet for NH at δ 12.12, doublet for imino proton (CH=N-) at δ 9.5, multiplet for four aromatic protons at δ 8.35–7.00, doublet for H-1 of the sugar at δ 5.15 and singlet for CH₂ at δ 4.0. The other proton signals of the sugar chain were congregated with the solvent absorption [(CD₃)₂SO] in a broad signal at δ 4.00–3.13 ppm. Moreover, the MS of **3c** and **3e** did not show their molecular ion peaks, but revealed characteristic fragments at m/z 172 (**4**), m/z 158 (**5**), m/z 147 (**6**), m/z 133 (**7**) and m/z 119 (**8**).

Table 1. Effect of tested compounds on granuloma formation^a

Test compound	Dry weight of granuloma (mg)	Granuloma inhibition ^b
Control	85.2 ± 2.20	–
Indomethacin	31.4 ± 1.00	63.14
3a	50.0 ± 1.66	41.31
3b	38.7 ± 2.21	54.58
3c	61.9 ± 2.59	27.35
3d	36.4 ± 1.37	52.28
3e	40.3 ± 2.11	52.70
3f	41.7 ± 1.42	51.06
3g	46.3 ± 1.18	45.66

^aMeans ± S.E. of 6 animals.

^bAll data are significantly different from control (P > 0.001).

The designed compounds were prepared according to the presented scheme: The Schiff bases (**3a-g**) were prepared by reaction of equimolar amounts of 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole (**1**) with aldoses (**2a-g**) namely: D-

Table 2. Physical data of aldehydo-sugar-(benzimidazol-2-ylmethyl)-imines (**3a-g**)

Compd ^a	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Colour	Molecular wt.	Molecular formula
3a	65	265	Brown	279	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄
3b	60	275	Red	279	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄
3c	75	285	Red	279	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄
3d	60	280	Red	279	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄
3e	80	270	Brown	309	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅
3f	75	290	Brown	309	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅
3g	65	295	Red	309	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅

^aAll the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

Antiinflammatory testing:

Adult male sprague-Dawley rats (120–149 g) were used. They were acclimated 1 week prior to use and allowed unlimited access to standard rate chow and water. Prior to the start of experiment, the animals were randomly divided into groups (6 rats each). Cotton pellet (35 ± 1 mg)

cut from dental rolls were impregnated with 0.2 ml (containing 0.01 mmol) of a solution of the test compound in chloroform or acetone and the solvent was allowed to evaporate. Each cotton pellet was subsequently injected with 0.2 ml of an aqueous solution of antibiotics (1 mg penicillin G and 1.3 mg dihydrostreptomycin/ml). Two pellets were implanted subcutaneously, one in each axilla of the rat, under mild general anesthesia. One group of animals received the standard reference indomethacin and the antibiotics at the same level. Pellets containing only the antibiotics were similarly implanted in the control rats. Seven days later, the animals were sacrificed and the two cotton pellets, with adhering granulomas, were removed, dried for 48 h at 60°C and weighed. The increment in dry weight (difference between the initial and final weights) was taken as a measure of granuloma \pm S.E. This was calculated for each group and the percentage reduction in dry weight of granuloma from control value was also calculated (Table 1).

The antiinflammatory activity of the synthesized compounds **3a-g** was evaluated employing the cotton-pellet granuloma bioassay in rats¹⁷ using indomethacin as a reference standard. The granuloma inhibition % values were determined for each compound (Table 2). Compounds **3b**, **3e**, **3d** and **3f** exhibited antiinflammatory activity comparable to that of the reference standard. Furthermore, compounds **3g** and **3a** exhibited moderate antiinflammatory activity while compound **3c** showed lower antiinflammatory activity than the reference standard. From this study it can be concluded that combination of methylbenzimidazole and imino-sugar moieties exhibit considerable antiinflammatory activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries using a MEL-TEMP II melting apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) : Perkin-Elmer FT Paragan 1000

spectrometer. ¹H NMR : Jeol ECA 500 spectrometer in DMSO(*d*₆), TMS as internal standard, chemical shift as δ (ppm). Mass spectra (MS) : Shimadzu GCMS-QP 1000Ex, 70 eV. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

General procedure for the preparation of aldehydo-sugar-(benzimidazol-2-ylmethyl) imines (3a-g) : A solution of 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole dihydrochloride¹⁸ (2.2 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was treated with NaHCO₃ (0.02 mol) till complete neutralization. After filtration, the ethanolic solution containing 2-aminomethylbenzimidazole **1** (1.47 g, 0.001 mol) was added to the respective sugar **2a-g** (0.001 mol) in H₂O (2 ml). The mixture was heated under reflux for 20 min and then left to attain room temp. The precipitated product was crystallized from aqueous ethanol (Table 2).

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